

The Role and Importance of Transformational Leadership in Ai-Based Management Processes

Yapay Zekâ Tabanlı Yönetim Süreçlerinde Dönüşümcü Liderliğin Rolü ve Önemi

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Öz

Yapay zekâ teknolojilerinin örgütsel yapılarda giderek artan kullanımı, liderlik anlayışları üzerinde derin ve dönüştürücü etkiler yaratmaktadır. Bu dönüşüm, liderlerin yalnızca kullandıkları yönetim araçlarını değil; aynı zamanda düşünme biçimlerini, karar alma yaklaşımlarını ve iş yapış süreçlerini de köklü biçimde yeniden şekillendirmektedir. Dijitalleşmenin hız kazanmasıyla birlikte yapay zekâ uygulamalarının yönetim süreçlerine entegrasyonu, geleneksel liderlik yaklaşımlarının dayandığı öngörülebilir ve görece durağan çevre koşullarını geçersiz kılmakta; bunun yerine belirsizlik, hız ve karmaşıklığın hâkim olduğu dinamik bir örgütsel yapı ortaya çıkarmaktadır. Bu bağlamda yapay zekâ, yalnızca operasyonel verimliliği artıran teknik bir araç değil; liderlerin sezgisel karar alma alışkanlıklarını sorgulayan, veriye dayalı düşünmeyi zorunlu kılan ve yönetsel sorumlulukları yeniden tanımlayan stratejik bir unsur olarak değerlendirilmektedir. Artan veri hacmi ve gelişmiş analitik kapasite, liderlik süreçlerinde doğruluk, şeffaflık ve hesap verebilirliği ön plana çıkarmakta; veri odaklı liderlik yaklaşımlarının önemini artırmaktadır. Ayrıca insan-makine iş birliğinin yaygınlaşması, liderlerin denetleyici rollerinden ziyade rehberlik eden, iş birliğini teşvik eden ve anlamlandırıcı rollere evrilmesini gerekli kılmaktadır. Bu çerçevede teknoloji farkındalığı, veri okuryazarlığı ve etik sorumluluklar çağdaş liderliğin temel bileşenleri hâline gelmektedir. Literatür, dönüşümcü liderliğin vizyoner yaklaşımı ve yenilikçiliği teşvik eden yapısı sayesinde yapay zekâ temelli dönüşüm süreçlerine yüksek uyum sağladığını ortaya koymaktadır. Bu çalışmanın amacı, yapay zekânın liderlik anlayışlarını nasıl dönüştürdüğünü incelemek ve dönüşümcü liderliğin bu süreçteki rolünü literatür temelli olarak açıklamaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler Yapay Zekâ, Yönetim, Liderlik, Dönüşümcü Liderlik.

Abstract

The increasing use of artificial intelligence technologies in organizational structures is creating profound and transformative effects on leadership approaches. This transformation reshapes not only the managerial tools used by leaders but also their ways of thinking, decision-making approaches, and work processes in a fundamental manner. With the acceleration of digitalization, the integration of artificial intelligence applications into management processes renders the predictable and relatively stable environmental conditions underlying traditional leadership approaches obsolete; instead, it gives rise to a dynamic organizational structure characterized by uncertainty, speed, and complexity. In this context, artificial intelligence is regarded not merely as a technical tool that enhances operational efficiency, but as a strategic element that challenges leaders' intuitive decision-making habits, necessitates data-driven thinking, and redefines managerial responsibilities. The increasing volume of data and advanced analytical capabilities bring accuracy, transparency, and accountability to the forefront of leadership processes, thereby increasing the importance of data-oriented leadership approaches. Moreover, the widespread adoption of human-machine collaboration requires leaders to evolve from controlling roles toward guiding, collaboration-enhancing, and sense-making roles. Within this framework, technological awareness, data literacy, and ethical responsibilities are becoming fundamental components of contemporary leadership. The literature indicates that transformational leadership, with its visionary approach and innovation-oriented structure, demonstrates a high level of alignment with artificial intelligence-based transformation processes. The aim of this study is to examine how artificial intelligence transforms leadership approaches and to explain, on the basis of the literature, the role of transformational leadership in this process.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Management, Leadership, transformative Leadership.

Introduction

The origin of the concept of artificial intelligence has been expressed as a logic based on Ancient Greece, which is based on the idea of attributing mind and motion to inanimate objects. It is seen that Daedalus, who made attempts to produce artificial humans, laid the foundations of artificial intelligence in this period. Artificial intelligence in the modern sense begins by aiming to define human thinking processes. In 1884, Charles Babbage's design of a mechanical machine capable of displaying intelligent human behavior is considered one of the major turning points in the history of artificial intelligence. In 1956, Dartmouth College officially coined the term "artificial intelligence" for the first time at a conference (Yılmaz, 2020). Although artificial intelligence is referred to as "artificial man" among the people (Aydın et al., 2018) describes systems that mimic human-like thinking and learning processes. Artificial intelligence is defined as machine-generated cognitive behaviors that are described as 'intelligent' when performed by man (Pirim, 2006). Artificial intelligence, one of the sub-disciplines of computer science, is expressed as a contemporary technical science that studies and develops theoretical approaches, methods, techniques and application systems aimed at simulating, expanding and improving human intelligence (Wang et al., 2023). With the rapid development of the use of artificial intelligence, not only the technical dimensions of this process, but also the understanding of leadership adopted in organizations play a decisive role. Leadership is defined as a phenomenon that expresses the process of initiating, sustaining and finalizing change processes in organizations, organizations, businesses and societies in today's world (Güney, 2012). According to Firestone (1996) leadership is expressed as a fact that should be performed for the organization to survive, develop and increase effectiveness, and the functions undertaken by the leader should be evaluated rather than what individuals in a certain office do. The conditions and contextual factors that enable the development of effective leadership are meant to help the corporate leader become better equipped to prepare and strengthen the environment that will support the growth of the

future leader (Vardiman et al., 2006). Although there are different types of leadership in the literature, it is seen that the core competencies of transformational leadership provide higher levels of efficiency in artificial intelligence processes. These competencies, including charisma and idealized influence (Altun, 2002), inspirational motivation (Erçetin, 2000), intellectual stimulation (Yavuz, 2002), and individualized consideration (Edizler & Akbulut, 2011), are addressed; these dimensions contribute to transformational leadership (Karip, 1998) by strengthening the alignment among people, technology, and organizational culture in AI-based transformation processes, thereby rendering it a leadership approach that stands out.

Because transformational leadership centers on intrinsic motivation and positive development of followers, it is considered a more attractive leadership approach than interactive leadership, which is based on extrinsic reward-punishment mechanisms and represents a relatively "mechanical" process of social change (Bass et al., 2006). Leadership is defined as the process of guiding individuals to act toward the achievement of organizational goals by influencing the organization's human resources. In this context, leadership is the shaping and directing of managerial processes within the framework of the competencies to be had and under different conditions, in such a way as to achieve individual or common goals (Ulukan, 2018). The diversification and rapid spread of artificial intelligence systems directly affect the structure and functioning of organizations. While these technologies have the potential to improve the performance of businesses, they can also pose a threat perception, especially in terms of managerial roles based on traditional leadership characteristics. However, at the intersection of artificial intelligence and creativity, individuals, teams and organizations are repositioned, and leadership roles are transformed within the framework of this interaction (Grilli, 2024). Global work dynamics are rapidly transforming due to AI-powered systems, robotics technologies, and the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This transformation is gaining an increasingly decisive position on a strategic level in the business world and reshaping the

competitive structures of organizations. Artificial intelligence applications increase the innovation capacity of organizations and at the same time enable the determination and achievement of targets that were difficult to foresee in the past (Erkutlu et al., 2023).

Artificial intelligence enables leaders to make decisions more systematically and faster. Therefore, leaders should see AI not as a threat to human resources, but as an element that can improve capacity. While the leader focuses on creative and strategic areas, artificial intelligence takes on routine and repetitive tasks. The integration of artificial intelligence into business processes is paving the way for comprehensive and multi-dimensional transformations in organizations (Sevinç, 2025). As artificial intelligence is integrated into business processes, leadership dynamics undergo a fundamental transformation, and this shift directs leaders to enhance their own competencies and to deploy intelligent systems effectively and responsibly (Sposato, 2024). In this context, to understand more systematically the leadership roles and competencies that transform with artificial intelligence, it is important to consider the historical development of the leadership phenomenon and the leadership theories that are reshaped with digital transformation.

Leadership theories and Digital transformation

Since the beginning of the twentieth century, interest in leadership has increased. While individual characteristics were prioritized in the early stages of leadership theories, many variables such as situational factors, behavior patterns and skill levels began to be discussed in the process. At present, there are numerous theoretical approaches aimed at explaining the concept of leadership and its applications (Maloş, 2012). Bass and Wren (1990) have classified leadership theories into various variables related to the nature and phenomenon of leadership. James (1880) argued that transformations in society were initiated largely by individuals who were described as “great men.” According to James, “the history of the world is the history of great men; it is they who make it possible for the masses to succeed.” Bass,

1990). As a result of this approach, the big men theory largely ignored the existence of female leaders, and leadership insight underwent a gender-based contraction (Landis et al., 2014).

Leadership has been a fundamental research topic in the field of organizational behavior that has always maintained its importance. Over time, many theories have been developed to explain leadership phenomena and leadership styles. Since an organization is made up of individuals who are operating towards specific goals, it always needs a leader to achieve these goals effectively and efficiently. Yukl (2002) defines leadership as “the process of influencing others to understand and agree on what needs to be done and how it can be accomplished effectively and facilitating individual and collective efforts to achieve shared goals” (Gregoire and Arendt, 2014). The role of the leader is critical to organizational success and cannot be ignored. The emergence of various leadership theories over time shows that the phenomenon of leadership is too complex to be explained by a single theory. Due to changing conditions, organizational contexts, and environmental dynamics, leadership approaches must also be adapted, as no theory fully fits all situations. In fact, it is known that the success or failure of many organizations is related to the leadership style that is applied to a significant extent. The literature shows that some organizations that were initially in a weak position have been revived and succeeded by appropriate leadership approaches (Deshwal, 2020).

Digital transformation plays a critical role in today’s rapidly changing technology ecosystem, not only for organizations to survive, but also for them to survive in the intense competition that globalization brings with it. Digital transformation is not only limited to the integration of technological innovations into business processes; it is addressed with the radical changes that have occurred in the understanding of corporate culture, organizational structure and management. This transformation process holds decisive importance for leaders in terms of business processes; leaders must not only adopt emerging technologies but also ensure that the transformation is directed across the entire organization in a holistic and consistent manner.

(Sunman, 2025: 613). At this point, to better understand the structural and managerial changes that digital transformation creates in organizations, it is necessary to examine the role of artificial intelligence as one of the primary driving forces of transformation in management processes.

The role of Artificial Intelligence in Management

In today's rapidly changing and competitive enterprises, accurate, reliable information is needed when making effective and informed decisions. Therefore, artificial intelligence and management information systems play a critical role in data collection, processing and transmission of this data to stakeholders. AI-powered systems play an important role in making management information systems smarter, more flexible and more effective through modeling such as big data analytics and machine learning (Berdibek et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence stands out within the wide range and dynamic structure of the business world with its increasingly developing strategic and technological infrastructure. In this direction, businesses gain a significant advantage in making their competitive advantage sustainable by adopting artificial intelligence technologies and integrating these technologies into their management processes (Berberođlugil, 2023). In today's business world, where technological progress is decisive, artificial intelligence is effective in radically transforming the understanding of leadership with traditional business conduct models by ensuring that the efficiency of enterprises increases, the margin of error is reduced, and the cost balance is optimized in the operational processes. (Akturan, 2024). Rapid adoption of artificial intelligence applications in many sectors, such as the health sector (Kına, 2025) and the education sector (İncemen et al., 2024, is transforming the ways in which jobs are created and automation skills; at the same time, it is seen to play an important role in decision-making processes within organizations (Bayar, 2024: 119). Artificial intelligence makes important contributions to improving brands' customer

experiences, increasing operational efficiency and personalizing marketing strategies. Artificial intelligence techniques used within the scope of big data analytics and machine learning play an active role in critical functions such as increasing customer satisfaction, product development and pricing. Rapid advances in technology in recent years have brought about significant transformations in many areas. In this context, digitalization has become a fundamental element in terms of increasing efficiency, reducing bureaucracy and strengthening individual-oriented service delivery. With the development of technology, administrative processes have been accelerated, transparency and efficiency increase in service delivery has been achieved. In this context, the adoption of artificial intelligence aims to improve the quality of services, to use resources more efficiently and to improve the service offered to individuals (Boyalı, 2025: 207).

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LEADERSHIP PRACTICES

Artificial Intelligence in Decision-Making Processes

The decision-making process starts with meeting the problems and needs, clearly stating the situations where the decision needs to be made and collecting the necessary data. Then, alternatives are developed to solve the problem and set goals (Coşkun, 2020). Artificial intelligence plays a major role in accelerating, facilitating and reducing margin of error in decision-making processes (İnce et al., 2021). Artificial intelligence applications accelerate decision-making processes by facilitating access to real-time information. Individuals in decision-making positions in businesses, along with the development of artificial intelligence-based solutions, must restructure traditional business processes and information systems (İnce et al., 2021). The success of organizations is measured by the level of achievement of the stated objectives and is evaluated as a managerial function. Both individuals and businesses benefit from the various alternatives they face at every stage of their lives and the

advantages offered by artificial intelligence in their decision-making processes (Karakasoğlu, 2008). In everyday life, individuals must constantly choose between various alternatives. Businesses also regularly enter decision-making processes to maintain their existence and provide a competitive advantage. In decision-making processes, artificial intelligence appears to play an important role in supporting, providing information and reducing uncertainty for individuals who are in the decision-making lens thanks to the ability to analyze rationally (İnce et al., 2021). Individuals have started to use artificial intelligence very often in decision-making processes with the development of artificial intelligence.

Data Driven Leadership Approaches

In today's data-intensive business environment, effective leadership is undergoing a transformation from intuition-based approaches to evidence-based approaches. Leaders encourage innovative practices and undertake extensive work to improve corporate performance to make informed and correct decisions. In the transition from traditional decision-making to data-centric strategies, technological developments and the impact of big data inputs on leadership practices play an important role. In this context, the basic process of data-driven leadership approach includes data collection, data analysis, data interpretation and visualization. The integrated integration of the components in this process effectively supports the actions in the leadership processes (Vadivelu, 2025). A team leader's core competence includes developing expertise and providing a work environment that encourages collaboration. The main goal of data-driven leaders is to systematically use data in daily business processes, draw meaningful conclusions from data, and strengthen team structure by creating a data-based business model (Schmidt et al., 2023).

Human-Machine Collaboration And Team Management

The proliferation of autonomous systems and the rapid development of artificial intelligence

will radically transform how and for what purposes humans and machines interact soon. In complex and dynamic areas such as industrial production, traffic and healthcare, human-machine interaction appears to increase operational efficiency and significantly reduce human workload. The integration of the complementary capabilities of man and machine enables the simultaneous utilization of both the cognitive capacity of man and the processing power of the machine (Alhaji et al., 2020). In different applications and functional situations where working people and machine team members work together, human-machine interaction is increasingly seen. Therefore, in artificial intelligence-assisted technologies, it is of great importance that the work is correctly defined and executed effectively in the joint task execution processes of the employees with the machines. The maintenance of team spirit in a manner compatible with business processes and the fair evaluation of employee performance should be supported by artificial intelligence technologies (Arslan et al., 2022).

Artificial Intelligence-Backed Strategic Planning

Strategic planning, which is one of the key components of strategic management, is expressed as a long-term and data-driven process aimed at ensuring that enterprises manage positions in an uncertain and proactive manner in their future planning. Artificial intelligence techniques appear to be important for strategic planning in solving these complex problems and minimizing the margin of error (Karatop, 2021). In today's rapidly changing technologies, artificial intelligence technology is increasingly being used to achieve a competitive advantage, especially in strategic decision-making processes (Aloamaka et al., 2025). From a strategic management perspective, it is seen that there are unstructured and uncertain issues in decision-making processes that require human judgment. It is seen that businesses with competitive advantage are starting to use artificial intelligence-assisted intelligent systems for extraordinary solutions. For example, hotel service robots aimed to study the perceptions of an integrated mechanical AI to customers' AI-powered hotel services (Mariani and Borghi,

2021). Artificial intelligence applications launched in the early period reveal that it can store expert information as a support tool in the decision-making process and can perform limited managerial actions at a strategic level. In the current situation, it is seen that the real value of artificial intelligence is its access to implicit information and its capacity to generate new information in which it performs unique analyses in different types of data (Keding, 2021).

Leadership Styles and Capabilities

Leadership theories have diversified over time, and different leadership styles such as characteristics, behavioral, situational, interactive and servant leadership are discussed in organizational context (Oğuz, 2011: 382). However, due to the nature of artificial intelligence-based transformation processes, this study focused solely on the transformational leadership approach. The main reason for this is that AI is not only a technical innovation in organizations, but also a strategic change that radically transforms the way they do business, decision-making processes, employee roles and organizational culture. Transformational leadership, with its ability to create visions, manage change, drive innovation, motivate employees in conditions of uncertainty and to observe individual differences, provides a more inclusive and descriptive framework for managing such radical technological transformations than other leadership styles (Bass, 1990; Karip, 1998; Yukl, 2013). Charisma-inspired motivations, intellectual stimulation and individual support capabilities of transformational leadership play a critical role in the adoption of artificial intelligence applications, reducing employee resilience, and ensuring sustainable human-machine collaboration. In this context, the theoretical focus of the study has been determined as transformational leadership because it is the leadership approach that is most compatible with artificial intelligence processes.

4.1. Transformational Leadership

Leadership function in the change process in organizations differs significantly from routine leadership practices. In the process of change, leaders need to question the current organizational functioning, create a vision and provide employees with a source of morale and motivation. Therefore, leadership characteristics in the transformational leadership approach should be addressed to cover both normal functioning and change processes (Karip, 1998). Transformational leaders are not only individuals who think, question and are willing to take risks, but also individuals who explain specific behaviors through the way they behave. Leaders are said to be individuals who promote entrepreneurship and individual development, including in traditional bureaucratic structures (Çelik, 1998). For this reason, transformational leaders see the changes that organizations need and manage the process effectively by making strategic plans for this change. To realize the transformation, it tried to carry out the process with a systematic approach (Şeker and Örucü, 2025). Transformational leadership is covered in literature within the framework of five basic sub-dimensions. These sub-dimensions are defined as including charisma (idealized influence) (Bass, 1990), individual support (Hinkin & Tracey, 1999), inspirational motivation (Karip, 1998), and intellectual stimulation (Karip, 1998); the aforementioned dimensions are regarded as the fundamental elements explaining the influence of transformational leaders on followers (Çelik, 1998).

4.1.1. Charisma or Idealized Leadership

Charisma, one of the key components of transformational leadership, refers to the perception of the leader by followers as someone who inspires trust, respect and admiration (Bass, 1990). In this context, the leader is seen as an individual who makes his followers feel trust in him and guides them in the direction of the goals set and motivates them to achieve success. This perceptual and emotional connection sets the stage for a strong identification process between the leader and the audience. As Altun (2002) puts it, "leaders are admired, respected, and

trusted. The followers identify themselves with their leaders. The leader is confident, committed, consistent and willing to take risks. Charisma is attributed to the leader by his followers." In this context, charisma is regarded as a fundamental element that is shaped by the perceptions of the followers rather than the personal characteristics of the leader and increases the effectiveness of transformational leadership.

4.1.2. Individual Support

In the transformational leadership approach, it is seen that individualized attention and understanding of the success of employees are adopted. Individuals with this understanding of leadership recognize that each employee is unique and provide instructional experiences that suit different needs. This approach supports the development of employees' skills and increases their motivation and commitment levels (Edizler and Akbulut, 2011). Individuals with transformational leadership characteristics ensure that employees develop as coaches and consultants within the organization by supporting their development and success. These leaders understand their potential by actively listening to individuals and distribute tasks accordingly. Following the deployment of tasks, it continuously monitors and analyzes employees, providing guidance and support where needed (Hinkin and Tracey, 1999).

4.1.3. Inspired Motivation

The leader stands out as both a source of motivation and an inspiring guide for those who follow him. Through symbols, slogans and simple emotional factors, a strong bond is established between the members of the group and contributes to the formation of a common consciousness in line with collective goals (Karip, 1998). The theoretical response of this process is explained by the concept of inspired motivation. Inspired motivation, in another definition, is "the process of creating vision, communicating vision, concentrating on the efforts of the audience using symbols, and modeling and creating appropriate behaviors." (Erçetin, 2000). Inspired by this aspect, motivation not only supports the followers to perform their duties, but also to engage with a

voluntary and high commitment to organizational goals.

4.1.4. Intellectual Stimulation

The leader aims to evaluate the current functioning, processes and cognitive structures of his followers in accordance with the core values of the organization and leadership. In the face of the challenges and problems encountered, the leader provides an environment to offer new perspectives and to produce alternative solutions so that the followers can develop different perspectives. In this context, the leader promotes an intellectual and innovative perspective, highlighting the function and impact of capacity for change (Karip, 1998). Transformational leaders, in their intellectual stimulation-driven management approach, encourage the transition from traditional methods to innovative and change-oriented approaches by enabling their followers to realize their creative potential (Yavuz, 2002).

4.1.5. Digital Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is a determining factor in the relationships that an individual establishes both with himself and with others. In other words, emotional intelligence plays an important role in the individual's own personal development and emotional formation, while on the other hand, it enables relationships with the environment to be carried out in a healthier, balanced and effective way through the abilities it possesses (Eymen, 2007). It is understood that emotional intelligence is a critical element in the leadership process, and it is not enough for leaders to have only technical and managerial skills. In addition, leaders need to have a high level of emotional intelligence and use this competency effectively in their business processes (Taskiran et al., 2016). Acar (2002) defines emotional intelligence as "a combination of social skills and abilities associated with the individual recognizing and controlling their emotions, providing self-motivation to achieve goals, and developing good relationships by understanding the feelings of the other party." With the increasing interest of emotional intelligence in management literature, it is seen that the relationship between leadership and

emotional intelligence along with its process has come to the forefront. In particular, the personal characteristics of emotional intelligence that affect the success of individuals in business life and the development of cognitive intelligence are of great importance for leadership (Downey et al., 200). The concept of emotional intelligence is closely related to transformational leadership. Sivanathan et al. (2002: 198) found that managers with high emotional intelligence in their work are perceived as transformational leaders by their subordinates. Similarly, a study by Cakar et al. (2003) concluded that emotional intelligence and transformational leadership have positive and meaningful relationships. Emotional intelligence has a multidimensional structure, and it is seen that dimensions have closeness within themselves. For example, it is seen that the individual is aware of his own feelings and understands the feelings of the other party better. But the relationship between the dimensions of emotional intelligence may not always be clear and linear. When emotional intelligence is taken as a whole, it is seen that it is used on a different level and in a different form in everyone. This suggests that leadership factors play an important role in differences in emotional intelligence processes (Erkuş et al., 2008). In this framework, the rise of traditional leadership approaches, as well as digitalization and technology-driven business environments, set the stage for the emergence of new dimensions in leadership understanding. In this context, both digital and shared leadership models play an increasingly important role in supporting effective decision-making and collaboration processes in modern organizations.

5. Digital, Traditional and Shared Leadership

Today's digital-intensive business environments are shaped by processes that force businesses to use technology and transformations in organizational structure. While digital technologies are changing in many areas, from communications to marketing, businesses need to be prepared to adapt to this change. Digital inadequacy and lack of preparation lead many businesses to fail in their digital transformation

processes. Therefore, in an intense competitive environment, it is imperative for businesses to develop new strategies. It seems that not only technological transformation, but also digital leadership plays a critical role for organizations to succeed in digital transformation (Onan, 2022).

Today, when digital transformation is inevitable, organizations need to have the necessary knowledge and skills in the process of digitalization. In this context, digital leadership plays a critical role in the acquisition of these knowledge and skills (Promsri, 2019). Digital leadership seems to have a complex and multidimensional structure. In this context, digital leadership adapts the role and style of leaders to the digital environment, while following a holistic approach covering mission, vision, values and organizational structure. In the light of these definitions, digital leadership effectively maintains individual management while ensuring the coordination of virtual teams as a leading actor in information flow, communication and innovative business models (Eberl and Drews, 2021). The digital leader is expressed as the person who enables the integrated use of tools and technologies in the digital age of management, management and strategic thinking styles under the interaction of different disciplines (Şahin et al., 2020). According to another definition, digital leadership is defined as people who strive to create a culture of sustainable change in organizations, use technology and strategy effectively in managerial processes, and adopt innovative innovation in organizations (Ordu and Nayır, 2020).

A new understanding of leadership based on human-machine interaction has emerged in order to complement the competencies of traditional leadership and achieve higher levels of responsibility and performance. In this context, it is important to synthesize systematic review findings in a holistic manner so that leaders can develop their fundamental competencies focused on artificial intelligence. (Hossain et al., 2025). These developments make it necessary for organizations to re-evaluate their understanding of management and their way of doing business. In addition, an understanding of

the fundamental differences between traditional leadership and digital leadership allows organizations to more effectively plan the role and functions of leaders in the process of digital transformation.

Table 1.

Traditional Leader Digital Leader differences

Digital leader	Traditional leader
Leads the change.	Manages the change.
Adopts the 'People First' principle.	Adopts the "Projects First" principle.
Encourages people to participate in the integration of technology.	Integrates technology without listening to the team.
Encourages employee participation in decision making.	Defines goals, vision and mission alone.
Accurately determines the nature and volume of the job.	Sets unrealistic goals.
Build trust and collaboration.	Works on their own.
Does not refrain from the transfer of authority.	Holds control.

Source: (Wirtz, 2021: 478).

Table 1 shows how digital leaders differ from the traditional leadership approach and what competencies stand out in the changing business environment. While integrating technology and a people-oriented approach, the digital leader exhibits leadership that promotes employee engagement and collaboration, which differs markedly from the one-way and control-oriented structure of traditional leadership.

In addition to traditional and digital leadership approaches, shared leadership understanding, where leadership responsibility is shared and employee engagement is at the forefront, is also an important option. Shared leadership is defined as a leadership approach with voluntary cooperation and mutual interaction of all stakeholders in the process in line with the realization of a common organizational goal (Aslan et al., 2015). In another definition, shared leadership is expressed as a leadership that provides a linear contribution to the competency and expertise processes of all employees within the organization; it is based on sharing leadership responsibility in organizations rather than gathering in a single individual (Göktaş et al., 2023). In this context, both digital and shared leadership play a critical role in helping organizations adapt to the changing business environment. The visionary and innovative approach of the digital leader and the participatory and collaborative structure of shared leadership offer a holistic leadership

model that strengthens both technological transformation and employee engagement in organizations. Thus, the traditional leadership approach evolves into shared leadership with the integration of digital tools and strategies and becomes a more flexible, participatory and adaptable leadership approach in organizations.

Technology Awareness and Data Literacy

The ability to access data and generate meaning from it supports the development of decision-making processes and policies at both individual and societal levels. Data-driven information access allows individuals and societies to adopt evidence-based approaches to policymaking. In this digital age, the effective use of data access on online platforms also increases the importance of digital and data literacy (Arik, 2024). In today's rapidly increasing reliance on digital technologies, it is seen that the level of individuals using technologies on online platforms, performing tasks for digitalization and using their related skills effectively is increasing. Digital skills have become a fundamental requirement for business sustainability, employee employment and economic growth, and have emerged as a critical issue of direct concern to the business community (Reddy et al., 2023). Martin (2006: 154) explains digital literacy as follows: "Digital literacy refers to the ability of individuals to interact with and understand and evaluate various digital tools used in many different areas of their work and private lives. This ability increases individuals' access to information, while also exposing them to many threats and risks in the digital world. Therefore, digital literacy education is vital for individuals to learn these skills and act safely and effectively in the digital world."

Deep-rooted transformations in digitalization significantly increase individuals' awareness of digital literacy. Especially in young individuals, perceptions and perspectives change significantly with rapidly developing technological innovations. Therefore, digital literacy-aware individuals can not only benefit from the technological possibilities they have experienced before but also create new and

independent spaces (Yaman and Elmaz, 2023).

Figure 1. Data literacy cycle (Arik, 2024: 60). (Adapted as cited in Enakrire, 2021.)

In Figure 1 shows the data literacy cycle. This cycle illustrates the basic steps of data literacy. This process allows individuals to make informed decisions by converting data into meaningful information. The importance of data literacy also necessitates the ethical and responsible management of artificial intelligence practices in leadership processes.

Ethical Leadership and Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence needs ethical discourse in terms of its future position and social impact. Today, the increasing involvement of computer technologies and artificial intelligence in human life raises concerns that it may lead to limitations in individuals' ability to think and do business. In the following processes, it is foreseen that this can cause various social problems and economic crises. Therefore, it is of great importance to address the ethical dimension of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence, while capable of analyzing errors in a human-like manner to prevent their recurrence, appears to have responses that differ from those of humans. To proceed objectively and systematically regardless of emotional factors, information must be properly recorded, and control mechanisms must be applied effectively in professional processes. (Dilek, 2019). Artificial intelligence, which plays an important role in human life by providing convenience, has long

been a subject of debate as to whether it can engage in reasoning grounded in moral principles. In this context, some scientists argue that artificial intelligence does not require ethical coding, and that the concept of ethics is inherently codable (Ersoy, 2018). When we assume that a robot or computer system has a high level of intelligence, the capacity to solve problems and be aware of its own consciousness, we see that this entity is not fundamentally different from human beings. Therefore, it is possible that human and robot technology can perform similar functions, have equivalent levels of consciousness and affordable experiences. The main difference that separates them is ontological. Therefore, it is suggested that, ethically, under certain conditions, human and advanced artificial intelligence entities may have the same status (Çelebi, 2017).

Artificial intelligence systems are defined as technological systems that offer functional benefits to individuals and institutions in many different application areas today; in the future, the need for human intervention is expected to decrease gradually. Increasing autonomy in AI-based systems necessitates the creation of an ethical framework, as these systems can operate under more limited human control. It seems that an ethical AI must adhere to principles and guidelines on fundamental issues such as individual rights, privacy, equality and non-discrimination. Ethical AI practices are seen to make significant contributions to improving the efficiency of organizations, reducing environmental impacts, strengthening public safety. However, artificial intelligence practices that are not based on ethical principles can lead to negativity in society (Turan et al., 2022). With the increasing use of artificial intelligence and other advanced technologies, the ethical application of these technologies is becoming increasingly important. While artificial intelligence creates important transformations in every area it affects, it brings with it various ethical problems. For this reason, the relationship between artificial intelligence and ethics needs to be constantly considered in the development and application of technology. Adherence to ethical principles makes it possible

to use artificial intelligence technologies in a sustainable and reliable way for the benefit of society. There are certain rules and frameworks that are effective in shaping and implementing ethical principles in the field of artificial intelligence.

1. **Data Privacy:** The artificial intelligence system is known to be based on large data sets. When collecting, processing and storing this data, the privacy of individuals is put at risk. That is why privacy is of great importance from an ethical point of view.
2. **Algorithmic Prejudice:** Artificial intelligence algorithmic values can reflect biases in the data sets they are trained on, so variables such as gender and age can have discriminatory consequences.
3. **Accountability in decision-making processes:** Artificial intelligence systems are capable of automated decision-making, and it appears that there are uncertainties about who is responsible for the consequences of these decisions.
4. **Transparency and explainability:** It is of great importance that artificial intelligence can understand which data it is based on and which processes it takes to make decisions. This transparency and explainability contribute significantly to the formation of social trust.
5. **Autonomous Systems:** Some artificial intelligence systems appear to operate autonomously without human intervention. This AI needs to clearly define its ethical boundaries, jurisdictions and responsibilities. Thus, it is protected from possible risk situations.
6. **Social and ethical norms:** The ethical acceptability of artificial intelligence can vary in terms of cultural, social and values. Therefore, universal ethical principles must balance among themselves in terms of local values (Keskin et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Ethical Principles of Artificial Intelligence (Karaağaçlı, 2025: 9)

As shown in Figure 2, the consideration of the ethical principles of artificial intelligence and the rules and frameworks established in this regard aims to ensure that artificial intelligence applications are designed and used in an ethical, reliable, and socially beneficial manner. In this context, the role of transformational leaders is especially important because they must not only manage technological processes but also ensure that ethical and responsible practices are integrated into the corporate culture.

Transformational leaders raise awareness of the potential risks and social impacts of artificial intelligence, promote ethical principles-aligned behavior models and promote ethical guidance in organizational decision processes. This approach ensures that AI technologies are developed and used in a manner that is not only efficiency or performance oriented, but also in accordance with societal values and human-oriented ethical standards. Therefore, in order for AI to be applied responsibly, transformational leaders need to play an active role at both the strategic and operational level, considering ethical principles.

Conclusion

As a result, this study demonstrates that the increasing use of artificial intelligence technologies in organizational structures is transforming leadership paradigms in a multidimensional manner. The findings of the literature show that artificial intelligence is not only a vehicle for efficiency in operational processes, but also a strategic element that

redefines decision-making, managerial responsibilities, and the leader-tracker relationship. With the acceleration of digitalization, it is seen that it is inevitable for leaders to move away from intuitive and experiential decision-making and to turn to data-based, analytical and transparent decision processes.

When the leadership approaches evaluated within the scope of the study are examined, it is concluded that transformational leadership is the leadership approach that provides the highest compliance to artificial intelligence-based transformation processes thanks to its features such as creating visions, encouraging intellectual stimulation and providing individual support. Transformational leadership stands out in its view of technological change not only as a technical necessity but as an opportunity for organizational learning, innovation and cultural transformation. This makes the role of the leader in guiding and making sense of artificial intelligence-assisted human-machine collaboration, team management and strategic planning processes even more important.

The compilation nature of the study means that the results obtained are limited to literature, but it offers strong conceptual implications regarding the relationship between artificial intelligence and leadership. In this regard, for future research, it is recommended to increase the number of empirical studies examining the effects of artificial intelligence applications on leadership behaviors across different sectors and organizational cultures. In addition, the development of integrated models that combine transformational leadership with digital, ethical and shared leadership approaches will make significant contributions to literature.

For practitioners, it is important to implement continuing education programs aimed at improving leaders' technology awareness, data literacy and ethical sensitivities. The effective, fair and human-oriented use of AI-powered systems depends on leaders adopting not only technical knowledge but also visionary, inclusive and responsible leadership. In this respect, the study provides a guiding framework for how leadership should be shaped in the age

of artificial intelligence, both in academia and in practice.

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Conceptualization: YMT, BE, ZEA

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Literature review: ZEA, YMT

Data collection and/or processing: YMT, ZEA, BE

Data analysis and/or interpretation: YMT, BE, ZEA

Writing - original draft: ZEA, YMT, BE

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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